

COMPARISON OF PER-OPERATIVE BLEEDING OF LIGASURE VERSUS CONVENTIONAL (MILLIGAN-MORGAN) HEMORRHOIDECTOMY FOR THE TREATMENT OF 3RD DEGREE HEMORRHOIDS

Dr. Sana Samad Khan^{*1}, Dr. Syed Shams ud Din², Dr. Umair Ahmad³, Dr. Bilal Hashim⁴,
Dr. Sufyan Yousaf⁵

^{*1,4,5}TRMO General Surgery, Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital (FGPC), Islamabad, Pakistan

²Consultant Surgeon, Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital (FGPC), Islamabad, Pakistan

³Medical Officer, Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital (FGPC), Islamabad, Pakistan

^{*1}sanasamadkhan@gmail.com, ²shamsfgpc@gmail.com

³umair.ahd000@gmail.com, ⁴bilalwattoo5723@gmail.com, ⁵sufyanousaf50@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20927758>

Keywords

Hemorrhoidectomy; Blood Loss, Surgical; Electrosurgery; Surgical Procedures, Operative; LigaSure

Article History

Received: 03 May 2025

Accepted: 30 May 2025

Published: 29 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Sana Samad Khan

Abstract

Background:

Hemorrhoidal disease is a common benign anorectal condition. Conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy remains the standard surgical treatment; however, it is often associated with considerable postoperative pain and delayed recovery. This study aims to compare the outcomes of LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy and conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy in patients with third-degree hemorrhoids to determine the more effective surgical approach.

Materials and Methods:

This randomized controlled trial was conducted at the Department of General Surgery, over 6 months. 240 patients with third-degree hemorrhoids underwent either LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy or conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy. Primary outcome was intraoperative blood loss, while operative time, hospital stay, and postoperative complications were assessed. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

Results:

A total of 240 patients were randomized equally into the LigaSure and conventional hemorrhoidectomy groups. LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy was associated with significantly lower intraoperative blood loss (18.6 ± 7.4 mL vs 42.3 ± 13.8 mL, $p < 0.001$), shorter operative time (21.5 ± 4.8 vs 29.8 ± 5.7 minutes, $p < 0.001$), and reduced hospital stay (1.2 ± 0.4 vs 1.5 ± 0.6 days, $p = 0.002$). Postoperative bleeding (3.3% vs 9.2%, $p = 0.048$) and anal discharge (15.0% vs 29.2%, $p = 0.008$) were significantly less frequent in the LigaSure group, while rates of fecal incontinence and anal stenosis were comparable between the two groups.

Conclusion:

LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy was associated with improved operative outcomes and fewer postoperative complications compared with conventional Milligan-

INTRODUCTION:

Hemorrhoidal disease is one of the most common benign anorectal disorders encountered in surgical practice worldwide. Hemorrhoids are normal vascular cushions located within the anal canal that contribute to continence; however, enlargement, prolapse, thrombosis, or bleeding of these cushions results in symptomatic hemorrhoidal disease requiring treatment.^{1,2}

The prevalence of hemorrhoidal disease has been reported to range between 4% and 39% in the general population, with peak incidence occurring between the fourth and sixth decades of life.^{2,3} Common symptoms include painless rectal bleeding, prolapse, mucus discharge, pruritus, discomfort, and, occasionally, acute thrombosis.² Surgical hemorrhoidectomy remains the gold-standard treatment for patients with advanced third- and fourth-degree hemorrhoids, particularly when conservative and office-based procedures fail to provide adequate symptom relief.^{3,4} Among surgical techniques, conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy remains widely practiced because of its effectiveness and low recurrence rate.^{3,4}

Despite its efficacy, conventional hemorrhoidectomy is associated with postoperative pain, bleeding, urinary retention, delayed wound healing, anal stenosis, and prolonged recovery.^{4,5} Consequently, several modifications and energy-based devices have been introduced to reduce tissue trauma and improve postoperative outcomes.^{5,6}

LigaSure is a bipolar vessel-sealing system that achieves permanent fusion of vessels with minimal lateral thermal spread. Studies have suggested that LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy may reduce operative time, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative pain, and hospital stay while maintaining comparable safety and effectiveness.⁶⁻⁹

Although several international studies have compared LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy with conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy, local evidence remains limited and conflicting.⁸⁻¹¹ Therefore, this study

was conducted to compare the outcomes of LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy and conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy in patients with third-degree hemorrhoids.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital, Islamabad, following approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB Reference No. FGPC.1/12/2023/Ethical Committee). The study was carried out over six months, from November 2024 to April 2025.

A total of 240 patients with third-degree hemorrhoids were enrolled after obtaining written informed consent. Sample size was calculated using the WHO Sample Size Calculator for comparison of two proportions. Patients aged 18–80 years of either gender diagnosed with third-degree hemorrhoids were included. Patients with recurrent hemorrhoids, first-, second-, or fourth-degree disease, hemorrhoids secondary to other anorectal pathologies, pregnancy, previous perianal surgery, or significant comorbid conditions affecting outcome assessment were excluded.

Eligible patients were randomized using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Allocation concealment was achieved through sequentially numbered opaque sealed envelopes opened immediately before surgery. Group A underwent LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy using the LigaSure Vessel Sealing System (Covidien, USA). Group B underwent conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy.

All procedures were performed by the same surgical team. Standard perioperative protocols were applied to both groups. Intravenous prophylactic antibiotics were administered at induction of anesthesia.

Primary outcome was intraoperative blood loss. For calculation of blood loss (in ml), dry surgical sponges and gauze pieces were weighed (in grams) prior to surgery. After completion of surgery, all

the gauzes and surgical sponges were weighed again. The difference in pre- and post-operative weight (in grams) was considered equal to amount of blood loss (in ml).

Secondary outcomes included operative time, hospital stay, postoperative bleeding, fecal incontinence, anal stenosis, and anal discharge. Patients were reviewed at postoperative day 5, one month, and three months.

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 23. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and compared using independent sample t-test. Qualitative variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages and

compared using Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

A total of 240 patients were included in the study. The mean age of patients in the LigaSure group was 43.8 ± 11.2 years, while the mean age in the conventional group was 45.1 ± 10.8 years. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups regarding age ($p=0.37$) or gender distribution ($p=0.61$). Baseline characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study population (n = 240)

VARIABLE	LIGASURE (n=120)	CONVENTIONAL (n=120)	p-VALUE*
Age (years)	43.8 ± 11.2	45.1 ± 10.8	0.37
Male	78 (65.0%)	74 (61.7%)	0.61
Female	42 (35.0%)	46 (38.3%)	

* $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

The mean operative blood loss was significantly lower in the LigaSure group compared with the conventional hemorrhoidectomy group (18.6 ± 7.4 mL vs 42.3 ± 13.8 mL, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, the

mean operative time was significantly shorter in the LigaSure group (21.5 ± 4.8 minutes) than in the conventional group (29.8 ± 5.7 minutes) ($p < 0.001$). This is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of Operative Outcomes

VARIABLE	LIGASURE (n=120)	CONVENTIONAL (n=120)	p-VALUE*
Blood loss (mL)	18.6 ± 7.4	42.3 ± 13.8	< 0.001
Operative time (minutes)	21.5 ± 4.8	29.8 ± 5.7	< 0.001
Hospital stay (days)	1.2 ± 0.4	1.5 ± 0.6	0.002

* $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Postoperative bleeding occurred in 4 (3.3%) patients in the LigaSure group and 11 (9.2%) patients in the conventional group ($p=0.048$). Fecal incontinence was observed in 1 (0.8%) patient in the LigaSure group and 3 (2.5%) patients in the conventional group ($p=0.31$). Anal stenosis developed in 2 (1.7%) patients in the

LigaSure group and 5 (4.2%) patients in the conventional group ($p=0.25$). Anal discharge was reported in 18 (15.0%) patients in the LigaSure group compared with 35 (29.2%) patients in the conventional group ($p=0.008$). This was shown in Table 3 and Figure 1.

Table 3: Comparison of Postoperative Complications

COMPLICATION	LIGASURE (n=120)	CONVENTIONAL (n=120)	p-VALUE*
Postoperative bleeding	4 (3.3%)	11 (9.2%)	0.048
Fecal incontinence	1 (0.8%)	3 (2.5%)	0.31
Anal stenosis	2 (1.7%)	5 (4.2%)	0.25
Anal discharge	18 (15.0%)	35 (29.2%)	0.008

* p ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Figure 1: Comparison of Postoperative Complications

DISCUSSION:

The management of advanced hemorrhoidal disease continues to evolve with the introduction of energy-based surgical devices aimed at reducing tissue trauma and improving postoperative recovery. Conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy remains one of the most effective procedures for third- and fourth-degree hemorrhoids; however, postoperative pain, bleeding, and delayed recovery remain important concerns.^{12,13} The present study compared LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy with conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy in patients with third-degree hemorrhoids and demonstrated favorable perioperative outcomes with the LigaSure technique.

In the present study, intraoperative blood loss was significantly lower in patients undergoing LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy compared with those treated by the conventional technique. This finding may be attributed to the vessel-sealing mechanism of LigaSure, which allows simultaneous coagulation and division of tissue with effective hemostasis.¹⁴ Reduced blood loss has been consistently reported in previous studies and is considered one of the principal advantages of the device.¹²⁻¹⁴

Operative time was also significantly shorter in the LigaSure group. Similar observations have been reported in previous randomized trials, where LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy required less operative time than conventional excisional

hemorrhoidectomy.¹⁵ In the study by Gentile et al., the mean operative time was significantly shorter in the LigaSure group than in the conventional diathermy group, supporting the efficiency of the vessel-sealing system.⁷

Hospital stay was modestly reduced among patients treated with LigaSure. Earlier recovery and reduced postoperative discomfort following LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy have also been reported by Bakhtiar et al., Haksal et al., and other comparative studies.^{8,10,12}

The incidence of postoperative bleeding was lower in the LigaSure group. Effective sealing of vascular pedicles may explain this reduction. Previous studies have reported either lower bleeding rates or comparable bleeding rates between the two techniques.¹⁵ Gentile et al. observed a trend toward fewer postoperative bleeding events in the LigaSure group, although overall complication rates remained similar between groups.⁷

In the current study, fecal incontinence and anal stenosis were infrequent in both groups, and the differences were not statistically significant. Similar findings have been reported in comparative studies where serious long-term complications were uncommon and largely related to surgical technique rather than the device itself.^{9,10,14} Preservation of adequate mucocutaneous bridges and careful dissection remain essential for preventing anal stenosis and sphincter injury.¹⁶

A notable finding was the significantly lower incidence of postoperative anal discharge among patients undergoing LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy. Reduced tissue trauma and limited lateral thermal spread may contribute to improved wound healing and decreased postoperative discharge.^{17,18}

Furthermore, the significantly shorter operative time and modestly reduced hospital stay in our LigaSure group corroborate the efficiency benefits reported in large randomized controlled trials, such as those by Wang et al. and Palazzo et al.^{19,20}

The study was conducted at a single center, which may limit generalizability of the findings. Additionally, longer follow-up would be necessary to assess recurrence rates and late postoperative complications. Future multicenter studies with extended follow-up periods are recommended to

further evaluate long-term outcomes and cost-effectiveness of LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy.

CONCLUSION:

LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy was associated with significantly lower intraoperative blood loss, shorter operative time, reduced hospital stay, and lower rates of postoperative bleeding and anal discharge compared with conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy in patients with third-degree hemorrhoids. Both procedures demonstrated comparable safety with respect to fecal incontinence and anal stenosis. LigaSure may therefore be considered an effective and safe surgical option for the management of advanced hemorrhoidal disease.

REFERENCES:

- Milligan ETC, Morgan CN, Jones L, Officer R. Surgical anatomy of the anal canal and the operative treatment of haemorrhoids. *Lancet*. 1937;230:1119-24.
- Ferguson JA, Heaton JR. Closed hemorrhoidectomy. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 1959;2:176-9.
- Chen JC, You JF. Current status of surgical treatment for hemorrhoids: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Chang Gung Med J*. 2010;33(5):488-500.
- Nienhuijs SW, de Hingh IH. Conventional versus LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy for patients with symptomatic hemorrhoids. *Int J Surg*. 2010;8(4):269-73.
- Mastakov MY, Buettner PG, Ho YH. Updated meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials comparing conventional excisional hemorrhoidectomy with LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy. *Tech Coloproctol*. 2008;12(3):229-39.
- Milito G, Cadeddu F, Muzi MG, Nigro C, Farinon AM. Haemorrhoidectomy with LigaSure versus conventional excisional techniques: meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Colorectal Dis*. 2010;12(2):85-93.

- Gentile M, De Rosa M, Carbone G, Pilone V, Mosella F, Forestieri P. LigaSure haemorrhoidectomy versus conventional diathermy for IV-degree haemorrhoids: is it the treatment of choice? *ISRN Gastroenterol.* 2011;2011:467258.
- Bakhtiar N, Moosa FA, Jaleel F, Qureshi NA, Jawaid M. Comparison of haemorrhoidectomy by LigaSure with conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2016;32(3):657-61.
- Ahire MD, Rathod CM, Baghadia S, Nandu B. Comparison study between vessel sealing technique and conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy. *Int J Surg.* 2016;3:1844-9.
- Haksal MC, Ciftci A, Tiryaki C, Yazicioglu MB, Ozyildiz M, Yildiz SY. Comparison of the reliability and efficacy of LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy and conventional Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy in grade III and IV hemorrhoids. *Turk J Surg.* 2017;33(4):233-6.
- Ghnam WM. Prospective randomized controlled trial of LigaSure versus conventional hemorrhoidectomy for grade III and IV hemorrhoids. *Int J Surg Med.* 2017;3(1):8-13.
- Islam MT, Rahman MH, Rahman MM, Ahmed S, Begum N. Randomized clinical trial of LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy versus open diathermy hemorrhoidectomy. *J Armed Forces Med Coll Bangladesh.* 2015;10(2):15-20.
- Talha A, Bessa S, Wahab M. LigaSure harmonic scalpel versus conventional diathermy in excisional hemorrhoidectomy: a randomized controlled trial. *ANZ J Surg.* 2017;87(4):252-6.
- Khanna R, Khanna S, Bhadani S, Singh S, Khanna AK. Comparison of LigaSure hemorrhoidectomy with conventional Ferguson's hemorrhoidectomy. *Indian J Surg.* 2010;72(4):294-7.
- Simillis C, Thoukididou SN, Slesser AA, Rasheed S, Tan E, Tekkis PP. Systematic review and network meta-analysis comparing clinical outcomes and effectiveness of surgical treatments for hemorrhoids. *Br J Surg.* 2015;102(13):1603-18.
- Sayfan J, Becker A, Koltun L. Sutureless closed hemorrhoidectomy: a new technique. *Ann Surg.* 2001;234(1):21-4.
- Kennedy JS, Stranahan PL, Taylor KD, Chandler JG. High-burst-strength, feedback-controlled bipolar vessel sealing. *Surg Endosc.* 1998;12(6):876-8.
- Altomare DF, Milito G, Andreoli R, et al. LigaSure Precise versus conventional diathermy for Milligan-Morgan hemorrhoidectomy: a prospective randomized multicenter trial. *Dis Colon Rectum.* 2008;51(5):514-9.
- Wang JY, Lu CY, Tsai HL, et al. Randomized controlled trial of LigaSure with submucosal dissection versus Ferguson hemorrhoidectomy for prolapsed hemorrhoids. *World J Surg.* 2006;30(3):462-6.
- Palazzo FF, Francis DL, Clifton MA. Randomized clinical trial of LigaSure versus open hemorrhoidectomy. *Br J Surg.* 2002;89(2):154-7.